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PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH**A NOVEL VALIDATED ASSAY METHOD FOR QUANTIFICATION OF FLUCONAZOLE IN MARKETED FLUCONAZOLE TABLET DOSAGE FORM BY ULTRAVIOLET SPECTROSCOPY: REVIEW****Khushali Deshmukh^{*}, Rashid Azeez, Vinod A. Bairagi***Department of Pharmaceutical Quality Assurance, K.B.H.S.S.Trust's Institute of Pharmacy & Research Center, affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University, Bhayegaon, Malegaon, Nashik, Maharashtra, India.***ARTICLE INFO****Article history**

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Validation.**ABSTRACT**

A simple, accurate, rapid and inexpensive UV spectrophotometric method was developed and validated for the determination of fluconazole in bulk and tablet doses. The drug is soluble in organic solvents such as ethanol and dimethyl formamide. Using the UV method, only fluconazole in tablet form can be measured easily, quickly and cost-effectively. The absorption maximum of fluconazole is between 200 and 260 nm. The proposed method was validated for linearity, precision, accuracy, sensitivity and robustness as per ICH guidelines. This review is very informative and you can easily measure fluconazole with this simple and accurate method.

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INTRODUCTION

Fluconazole is known chemically as [2-(2,4,-difluorophenyl)-1,3-bis(1H1,2,4,-triazol-1-yl) propan-2-ol]. Fluconazole is an official drug in the United States Pharmacopoeia, European Pharmacopoeia, and British Pharmacopoeia. A broad-spectrum antifungal derived from synthetic bitriazole, it is effective against a variety of topical and systemic fungal infections orally and orally. It is recommended for the treatment and prevention of the spread of oropharyngeal, esophageal or vulvo-vaginal candidiasis and deep visceral candidiasis. Patients who are prone to yeast infections receive chemotherapy or radiation therapy with this drug before undergoing a bone marrow transplant to prevent yeast infections. Fluconazole is a highly selective C-14 sterol inhibitor of fungal (X-demethylated) cytochrome P450. Therefore, this drug inhibits cell membrane formation by inhibiting ergosterol synthesis (Figure 1) [3].

It appears as a white crystalline powder, sparingly soluble in water and very soluble in alcohol. Fluconazole inhibits the enzyme 14 α -demethylase fungi cytochrome P450 [4]. Fluconazole is mainly a bacteriostatic antifungal. However, it can have a dose-dependent fungicidal effect against some microorganisms, especially cryptococci. Fluconazole is active against these microorganisms: *Blastomyces dermatitidis* *Candida* spp. (except *C. krusei* and *C. glabrata*). Side effects associated with fluconazole treatment include: Common (more than 1% of patients): skin rash, headache, headache, nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, diarrhea, increased liver enzymes. Fluconazole is excreted in breast milk with concentrations similar to those in plasma. Therefore, the use of fluconazole in nursing mothers is not recommended. Some people are allergic to azoles, so people who are allergic to other azole drugs may also be allergic to fluconazole. This means that some azole drugs can have side effects. Some azole medications can interfere with estrogen production during pregnancy and affect the outcome of the pregnancy. Fluconazole at a dose of 150 mg is classified as FDA pregnancy category C [5].

Side effects associated with fluconazole treatment include skin rash, headache, dizziness, nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, diarrhea, and/or liver enzymes. Fluconazole is excreted in breast milk with concentrations similar to those in plasma. Therefore, the use of fluconazole in nursing mothers is not recommended. Some people are allergic to azoles. Some azole drugs can interfere with estrogen production during pregnancy and affect pregnancy outcomes [2].

Figure 1: Chemical structure of Fluconazole.

Table 1: Drug profile of fluconazole.

Generic Name	Fluconazole
Brand Name	Diflucan
IUPAC Name	2-(2,4,-difluorophenyl)-1,3-bis(1H1,2,4,-triazol-1-yl)propan-2-ol
Chemical formula	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ F ₂ N ₆ O
Molar Mass	306.277 g.mol ⁻¹
Protein binding	11-12 %
Synonyms	Diflucan, Difluconazole, Fluconazol, Fluconazolium.
Melting point	139 °C
Elimination half life	30 hrs

HPLC Method:

A literature review revealed several HPLC methods for the quantitative determination of fluconazole in pharmaceutical formulations using variations in mobile phase, column, and detector. There are various HPLC methods for FLC in the official pharmacopoeia for individual studies, and several LC-MS/MS methods have been used to determine FLC in human plasma. Therefore, an attempt was made to develop a simple, efficient and selective RP-HPLC method for the intracellular measurement of FLC concentration and use it in azole-resistant *C. albicans* [6].

Principle:

HPLC is a separation technique. A small amount of liquid sample (3 to 5 microns (μm) in diameter, called the stationary phase) is injected into a tube and individual portions of the sample are separated. The bottom of the tube fills up. The liquid (solid phase) is injected into a tube (column) and enters the pressurized column at high pressure delivered by a pump. These components are separated by columnar packing, which involves various chemical and/or physical interactions between the molecules and the packing particles [7]. At the outlet of the pipe (valve), this ratio is detected by a flow device (detector) that measures its value. The output of this detector is called "HPLC". In theory, LC and HPLC work similarly, but HPLC excels in speed, efficiency, sensitivity, and ease of operation. Although HPLC retains much of its analytical reliability, simple liquid chromatography principles are used for primary purposes. As shown in the schematic diagram above, an HPLC instrument consists of a solvent reservoir, a pump, an injector, a column, a detector, an integrator or absorber, and a display system. The main part of the system is the separation column [7,8].

UV spectroscopy:

Ultraviolet (UV) spectroscopy is a physical optical spectroscopy technique that uses light in the visible, ultraviolet, and infrared ranges and is based on the Beer-Lambert law, which states that the absorbance of a solution is directly proportional to its concentration. Mass absorption modes and path lengths in solution. Therefore, if the path length is constant, it can be used to determine the concentration of the adsorbent in the solution. Because of the need to know the rate of change in absorption and concentration, UV-VIS spectroscopy has been used continuously for the past 37 years and has become one of the most important analytical techniques and revolutionary tools in modern laboratories. . Although other methods can be used in many applications, it does not compete with UV-VIS spectroscopy in terms of simplicity, versatility, accuracy, speed, and cost-effectiveness [6,9].

Principle of UV spectroscopy:

Molecules or ions absorb in the visible or ultraviolet region when radiation causes electronic transitions in their structure. Therefore, the absorption of light by the sample in the ultraviolet or visible region requires a change in the electronic state of the molecules in the sample. The energy provided by the light drives the electron into a higher energy, excited state, or anti-bonding orbital, from its ground state orbital. There are three types of Earth's orbit [10].

1. σ (Bonding) molecular
2. π (Bonding) molecular orbital
3. n (non-Bonding) atomic orbital.

Figure 2: Instrumentation of UV-Spectroscopy.

From the literature review, it was found that several gas chromatography [11,12], microbiological methods [13] and HPLC detection methods [14-16] have been performed on different formulations of fluconazole. There are methods to assess fluconazole alone or in combination with body fluids such as serum [17-19]. Combined UV spectrophotometry has been reported to measure fluconazole in eye drops or in combination. However, no method has been found to estimate fluconazole in tablet doses using UV spectroscopy. This shows that until now there is no UV method for the estimation and determination of fluconazole in tablet dosage form [20].

METHOD DEVELOPMENTS:**Instruments:**

The Shimadzu Double Beam UV-Visible Spectrophotometer 1700 Ultra is an ideal partner. Quartz cell, bath sonicator, and civilian balance capable of 1 cm optical path length and 1 nm spectral bandwidth. An Equiptronics melting point device was used [21].

Determination of λ max (100 PPM):

100 mg of fluconazole was dissolved in a 100 ml volumetric flask. Pour the tube into a 10 ml 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolve and label. This solution was scanned from 200 to 400 nm to determine the absorption maxima [21].

Selection of detection Wavelength:

To determine the λ peak of fluconazole, a solution of 10 μ g/ml fluconazole in CH₃OH was prepared and scanned at a UV wavelength between 200 and 400 nm. When using a solvent ratio of methanol to water (50:50), the maximum UV λ max was obtained at 260 nm [22].

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution:

An exact weight of 10 mg of fluconazole was dissolved in 10 mg of methanol: water (50:50) in a 100 ml volumetric flask. Prepare a stock solution of 100 μ g/ml fluconazole in the above solution by sonication. A solution of methanol: water (50:50) contains a concentration between 20 and 100 μ g/ml [23].

Figure 3: UV Visible Spectra of Fluconazole.

Preparation of Calibration curve:

Appropriate dilutions were prepared from the fluconazole stock solution prepared above to obtain final concentrations of 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 μ g/mL, and the λ max absorbance at 260 nm was measured. The average value of these five sets, the standard calibration curve, and the calibration curve are plotted. Eye doses are used with concentrations from 20 to 100 μ g/ml. Linearity was calculated using the least squares regression method. Fluconazole calibration data is shown in Table 1. Figure 2 shows the calibration curve of fluconazole [24].

VALIDATION OF METHOD DEVELOPMENT:

The proposed method was developed in 1996 based on ICH guidelines with linearity, accuracy, precision and robustness.

Linearity and Range:

Different amounts of fluconazole were extracted from 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 ml of stock solution using methanol:water solution (50:50) in 10 ml and 20 concentrations of $\sim$ 100 μ g. / accepted. Absorbance at 260 nm of each concentration was recorded after each milliliter and the calibration graph of absorbance against each concentration was plotted. The beer rule was followed in the range of 20–100 μ g/ml [25].

Precision:

A detailed study was conducted to confirm the reproducibility of this method. Reproducibility is determined by repeating the sample six times at the same concentration and measuring absorbance. A detailed study at home was done by analyzing the drug solution prepared three times a day (8-hour sampling). The same procedure was repeated on three different days to measure daily accuracy. The results are reported as %RSD [21].

Accuracy:

To ensure the accuracy of the method, three sample solutions were prepared at a concentration of 80, 100 and 120%, each sample solution containing an amount of active drug and a volumetric solution of 100 ml of analytical grade. Recovery tests are done by dilution in flasks. Measure the absorbance at 252 nm [2].

Table 2: Accuracy study (Spectrophotometric method).

Accuracy (%)	Quantity weighed (mg)	Quantity found (mg)	Recovery (98-102%)
80	0.8	0.79	98.75
100	1.0	1.01	101.00
120	1.2	1.21	100.83

Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of quantification (LOQ) [26,27]:

LOD is the lowest detectable amount of analyte in a sample. LOQ is the lowest amount of an analyte in a sample that can be calculated with quantitative accuracy and precision. LOD and LOQ are calculated by the following formula.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3\sigma/S,$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \sigma/S.$$

Where,

σ is the standard deviation of the Y intercept of the calibration curve and S is the slope of the regression equation. The linearity equation was found to be $y = 0.0017x + 0.0547$.

The LOD and LOQ values were found to be 6.563741 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 19.89012 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively.

Robustness:

To determine the reliability of the method analysis was carried out using a standard at a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at two different wavelengths and at room temperature, and the corresponding absorbance was measured [23].

Repeatability

A concentration of 240 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ was prepared from a stock solution of fluconazole and its absorbance was measured against 0.1 N hydrochloride at a wavelength of 239 nm. standard deviation and relative deviation were calculated [28].

Reproducibility

The 300 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ solution was prepared separately from the fluconazole stock solution and analyzed at 239 nm by the analyzer (analyte 1). The same solution was prepared by another analyst and the values obtained were evaluated using a t-test to ensure reproducibility [29,30].

CONCLUSION

A method for the estimation of fluconazole in tablets has been developed. A UV method was developed for the evaluation of fluconazole. This method provides results with high precision, accuracy and reproducibility and can analyze low concentrations of fluconazole. This shows that the developed spectroscopy method is simple, linear, precise, reliable and accurate for estimating fluconazole in tablet dosage form. Therefore, this method can be considered to determine fluconazole in tablet dosage form in the quality control laboratory.

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